

Ambiance that Keeps You Coming Back: Exploring Customer Satisfaction and Revisit Intention in Coffee Shops

¹Isaac Daniel Goldwayne CORONEL, ²Fernando BACAR,
³Christian Ziggen MANUEL, ⁴Marichou Fabregas Seniorin

^{1,2,3} Researchers, ⁴Adviser:

De La Salle University – Dasmariñas

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11353585>

Published Date: 27-May-2024

Abstract: Coffee shops is known to be a place where you can relax, chill, do work, study or just have a cup of coffee and as years past by coffee shops have evolved, not only coffee shops but also its consumers. The present study investigate the effect of physical ambiance on the revisit intentions of customers in coffee shops. Now that coffee shops is popular in different ages of people, the researchers aims to know what attract them the most, mainly on physical manners. Participants from three different coffee shops will take a survey and rate how does this characteristics of a coffee shop affects their revisit intentions on that place. The deeper we get to this study we understand what makes coffee shops click to the consumers to this year and years to come

Keywords: coffee shops, ambiance, physical ambiance, customer satisfaction, revisit intentions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Coffee shops are known to be one of the most visited places nowadays, since they are planned to be comfortable and welcoming, with warm lighting, cozy seating, and a relaxed ambiance. This kind of environment makes people feel more comfortable and relaxed, which can help them to be more productive and creative. Individuals spend their budget on coffee consumption mainly because it serves as a multi-beneficial investment for studying, working, and socializing.

The growing demand for coffee shops increased the industry's competitive condition and has caused each brand to seek innovative strategies. Most coffee shop businesses try to provide their customers with a strong level of experience not only with the quality of food they serve but with the ambiance of their place as well. The ambiance of a coffee shop is very important in defining the customer's experience, which Truic (2023) proved in his study that a cafe's ambiance improves the customer experience more than many business owners realize. The ambiance of a coffee shop not only shapes the initial impression created by customers but also has a substantial impact on their overall mood, Pangaribuan, & Sitingjak (2019) found out in their study that the atmosphere of a café has a significant relationship with customer satisfaction and that customer satisfaction and revisit intention are interrelated. However, there is a distinct difference in previous research, specifically in the context of coffee shops' location. Previous research studies have been conducted in places like-----but none of this kind has been done in Tagaytay, this is the reason why the researchers want to explore and make this place the subject of this research.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research aims to understand and know how ambiance mainly physical ambiance affect the customers satisfaction and revisit intentions; the goal of the thesis is:

1. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, occupation, income level and frequency of visit.

2. Determine the level of customer satisfaction in terms of decorations and artifacts, lighting and music, store layout and cleanliness.
3. To determine what is the level of customers' intention to revisit.
4. To determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of customer satisfaction and intention to revisit.

SETTING OF THE STUDY

Tagaytay, a renowned Philippine tourist destination, is noted for its temperate environment, picturesque views, and numerous gastronomic choices. The city attracts a great number of visitors, both domestic and international, who seek respite from the bustling urban environment and immerse themselves in the area's calm ambiance. Coffee shops have become an essential component of Tagaytay's thriving food and beverage sector. With its warm atmosphere and scenic surroundings, the city is a great place to have a cup of coffee while admiring the stunning views of Taal Lake and Volcano. Coffee shops in Tagaytay not only provide a pleasant and friendly ambience but also a variety of specialty coffee blends and delectable pastries that cater to the different preferences of both locals and tourists.

As per BMPlus (2023), Coffee shops and cafe restaurants are booming and are opening hand over fist everywhere in Tagaytay. It is believed that every city has its own personality — a character that makes it special. In addition, Tagaytay has been everyone's fastest escape from the hustle and bustle of the city, so if someone is longing for a good cup of coffee in great cold weather, there's no place you'd rather be. An Instagram-worthy Cafe and every detail has a story. A quaint space inside that would let you start a conversation and build new friendships over time. They believe that every city has its own personality — a character that makes it special. In addition,

These Tagaytay coffee shops have developed beyond pouring coffee to become social and cultural hubs, attracting people from all walks of life. Visitors are frequently seen conversing, working remotely, or simply releasing their coffee while immersing themselves in Tagaytay's peaceful and laid-back ambience.

Tagaytay's coffee shop scene is distinguished by a blend of modern and rustic aesthetics. Many places have sleek and modern interiors, with comfortable seating arrangements, trendy design, and carefully selected lighting that creates a friendly and welcome atmosphere. Some coffee shops, on the other hand, embrace a rustic charm, including elements such as wooden furnishings, vintage accents, and earthy color schemes that combine nicely with Tagaytay's natural beauty. Coffee shops in Tagaytay frequently prioritize individualized and attentive service to their clients, in addition to creating a calm and warm setting. Baristas and staff members are noted for their cheerful demeanor, participating in polite conversations, and providing individualized recommendations depending on the tastes of their clients. This focus on customer service improves the overall coffee shop experience in Tagaytay.

Overall, Tagaytay coffee shops have become popular locations for both locals and tourists, providing not only a broad variety of coffee beverages but also a refuge where people can unwind, connect, and appreciate the city's particular beauty. Tagaytay's natural beauty, comfortable climate, inviting environment, and quality coffee options make it an appealing place for coffee connoisseurs and contribute to the area's burgeoning coffee culture.

Fig.1: Map of Tagaytay

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aims to explore customer experiences regarding the ambience of coffee shops in Tagaytay and its impact on customer satisfaction and revisit intention. Tagaytay is a popular tourist destination known for its scenic views and cool climate, making it an ideal location for coffee shops. The ambience of a coffee shop can play a significant role in the overall customer experience and ultimately influence their revisit intention.

This study specifically aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents, in terms of:

1.1. Age

1.2. Gender

1.3. Occupation

1.4. Income Level

1.5. Frequency of visiting (weekly)

2. What is the level of customer satisfaction in terms of:

2.1. Decorations and artifacts

2.2. Lighting

2.3. Music

2.4. Store layout

2.5. Cleanliness

3. What is the level of customers' intention to revisit?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of customer satisfaction and intention to revisit?

STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESIS

There is no significant relationship between the cafe ambience and customer satisfaction in their revisit intentions of selected coffee shops in Tagaytay.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Coffee shops offer visitors the opportunity to relax, chat with friends or make new friends, as well as serving a wide range of beverages and patisserie products. Although people of different ages and status can still be found in these shops, which have a social characteristic (Bayındır & Öncel, 2019), it is accepted that boutique coffee shops are generally preferred by conscious consumers who attach importance to the quality and aroma of coffee beans (Tüzün, 2018). The fact that consumption in coffee shops has gone beyond an ordinary eating and drinking activity and gained different emotional and social dimensions is a transformation that has occurred as a result of a series of stages.

Heung and Gu (2018) stated five atmospheric aspects in their study: facility aesthetics, ambience, spatial layout, employee factors and window in a restaurant setting. The facility aesthetics dimension refers to interior design and décor. The background music, aromas, lighting and temperature comprise an ambience aspect. Khare (2018) investigated seven attributes with respect to coffee shops' involvement behavior as ambience, design, interiors, service, assortment, socializing and entertainment. In this study ambience is defined by including music, color, facilities and layout. Design implies color schemes, spaciousness, product and service availability etc. Through service factors tested the influence of staff behavior. Also stated by C. Pangaribuan, A. Sofia, M. Sitinjak (2019) that it is important to make the coffee shop as comfortable. Creating a good ambience by setting the right lighting would be preferable. Heung and Gu (2018) stated patronage concept as a component of behavioral intention and which refers to consumers' return intention to a same restaurant setting and revealed that aesthetic and pleasing environments are strongly affecting customer patronizing.

Research on the sensory marketing approach (Jang and Lee, 2019) is a relevant basis for explaining the effect of sensory experiences on brand love in this study. The research has identified several sensory aspects that are commonly used in any

coffee shop marketing strategy. The study confirms that the factors of taste, vision, scent, and touch regarding the product have a significant positive effect in influencing customers' emotional reactions. Findings in other studies also confirm that consumers often involve sensory experience in determining their favorite brand. Those findings show that Starbucks consumers in India will consider other essential aspects besides the coffee quality, such as interior design, music selection, and unique wall painting-based. Noice (2023) also stated that ambient noise reportedly improves focus and productivity by helping to reduce distractions and increase cognitive performance. Studies have found that the right level of ambient noise can enhance creativity, improve memory retention, and even boost mood

The study of Duman (2020) states that ambience plays a crucial role in creating a positive experience for customers in the food and beverage industry. Experts in the F&B and hotel industries stress the importance of selling "experience" and "sensory experiences" in restaurants, with the ambience appealing to customers' other senses in addition to taste. Duman defines ambience as a design element that aims to elicit specific emotional responses from customers. In today's market, customers not only look for good food but also excellent service and a pleasant dining environment.

Decoration and artifacts are the physical environment that induces perceptual and emotional responses among customers that affect the consumer's revisit intention AbuThahir, S; Krishnapillai, G. (2018). Meanwhile, Han, H., Lee, K., Song, H., Lee, S., & Bee-Lia Chua. (2019) stressed that the decorations and artifacts of the café not only create aesthetic impressions, but are also employed as an indicator of differentiation of the chosen dining environment which leads to the customer's revisit intention.

According to AbuThahir, S; Krishnapillai, G. (2018), lighting affects customer's behavior in restaurants and explains that lighting influences customer's emotions, mood, and cognition. Dimmed lighting creates an intimate environment for the customer however, Jacquier and Giboreau (2018) indicated that brightness of the lighting is important for customers to read the cafes' menu. Han, H., Lee, K., Song, H., Lee, S., & Bee-Lia Chua. (2019) supported that lighting elements of the store have a great impact on the customer intention to visit the retailer for repurchase action. Moreover, the customers believe that the pleasant lighting in the café indicates the quality of the service provider.

Customer preferences towards music affect their customer satisfaction AbuThahir, S; Krishnapillai, G. (2018). Hence, Han, H., Lee, K., Song, H., Lee, S., & Bee-Lia Chua. (2019) explained that café owners should fine-tune background music by changing its volume (i.e. loud to soft), tempo (i.e. fast to slow), and genre (i.e. classical or jazz), based on customer's interest to arouse consumers' emotional states. Similarly, music has an impact on emotions, mood, and pleasure. Furthermore, Rea, MacDonald, and Carnes (2019) agreed that the mood of the listener can be positively or negatively influenced depending on the type of music played. They added that classical and pop music increases the listener's feeling of ease and decreases feeling of worry or tension.

VanBaren (2019) claimed that the store layout is the design of a store's interior to provide maximum exposure of merchandise. Well-planned layouts are essential to facilitate in-store traffic patterns and increased customers' efficient movement through the store. Store layout in café should emphasize on the seating arrangement, equipment and furnishing which increases customer satisfaction and leads them to spend longer hours in the café. Hence, those items are able to facilitate café performance in increasing customer revisit intention.

AbuThahir, S; Krishnapillai, G. (2018) stated that the cleanliness of café affects the customer's feelings towards the café whether to revisit the café again in the future. Furthermore, the level of cleanliness is able to create an image of comfort and luxury among customers' which affects the customer's revisit intention.

The external variables such as location, accessibility indicated as crucial atmospheric to grab customers to shopping malls since it is more convenient for customers and revealed that location and easy accessibility to store as an important attribute for customers regarding behavioral intention. Ong, C. H., Lee, H. W., & Ramayah, T. (2018).

Berman & Evans (2018) recognized four types of atmospheric variables: Store exteriors, store interiors, layout & design and point of purchase & decoration. Store exteriors consist of store front, entrances, window displays, physical characteristics of the building, surrounding area, and parking. The flooring, coloring, lighting, sounds, fixtures, merchandise and cleanliness including to store interiors. The floor space allocation was exhibited as layout & design. The point of purchase & decoration includes wall decorations, point of purchase displays, signs, pictures and arts, price and product displays.

The physical environment comprises lighting, decoration, layout, and employee appearance (Rather, Najar, & Jaziri, 2020; Ryu & Han, 2010; Saaidin et al., 2018). These factors are significant in promoting an attractive ambience and a good image,

affecting the customer's intention to patronize the restaurant business (Adnan & Valliappan, 2019; Ariffin, Bibon, & Abdullah, 2017; Tuzunkan & Albayrak, 2016). For the most part, the physical environment of an Islamic restaurant includes the general layout, structure, decoration, and style (Kim, 2012; Lee & Jeong, 2012). and these will have a positive impact on customer satisfaction (Han & Hyun, 2017; Lee & Jeong, 2012; Sikiru & Raju, 2020). A conducive and superior physical environment also encourages young customers to further consider repeat visits (Ali et al., 2013; Canny, 2014; Raju, 2019). Ali and Amin (2014) and Pressly and Heesacker (2001) conclude that customers become increasingly receptive when they enjoy the expected physical environment in Islamic restaurants that tends to increase their intention to revisit.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

The study will be guided by the independent and dependent variable framework which is used to test the cause and effect of a particular variable to another. Ambiance in this study is the independent variable to be tested on its effect to the revisit intention which is the dependent variable. A mediating variable will also be observed which is “customer satisfaction” on how the independent and dependent variables are related.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Quantitative study is an exploratory study, which is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data. It can be used to find patterns and averages, make predictions, test causal relationships, and generalize results to wider populations. Bhandari, P. (2020). It aims to gain an understanding of customer experiences and perceptions regarding the ambience of coffee shops and its impact on their satisfaction and revisit intention. Exploratory studies are often used in the early stages of research to gather information and generate ideas for future research.

Purposive Sampling Method (Quota Sampling)

The researcher will only use purposive sampling technique in this study, which is a technique in which units are selected because they have characteristics that you need in your sample. In other words, units are selected “on purpose” in purposive sampling. This method is useful for specific populations and for studying sensitive topics. Nikolopoulou, K. (2022)

Participants of the Study

This study’s participants are customers of selected coffee shops in Tagaytay. The main basis of the researcher is that the cafe should still be existing before the pandemic and post pandemic. (54 each)

Bag of Beans, Tagaytay	Cafe Voi La, Tagaytay	Tsokolateria, Tagaytay
8 years of service (since 2015)	6 years of service (since 2017)	7 years of service (since 2016)
Top 4 coffee shops in Tagaytay (ref. guide to the philippines travel tips)	Top 10 coffee shops in Tagaytay (ref. guide to the philippines travel tips)	Top 5 coffee shops in Tagaytay (ref. guide to the Philippines travel tips)
One with the best scenic view of the Taal Volcano	Known for their Thai restaurant and cafe aesthetic. Also for their vegan friendly foods.	Known for their chocolate creations and wide array of beautiful dinnerware pieces such as plates and

Rank 1 in terms of desert (ref. tripadvisor)	Rank 6 of 96 Asians in Tagaytay (ref. tripadvisor)	glasses Rank 31 in terms of desert (ref. tripadvisor)
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Data Gathering

To begin with the data-gathering procedure, the researcher will prepare a consent letter to the coffee shop that we choose that will allow us to conduct a survey to the customers that will be signed by the one who is in-charge of the coffee shop. Same with the customers, we will prepare consent forms that will be signed by the respondents, which indicates that they agreed to the researcher's use of their answers for the purpose of the study. The consent form will ensure that the respondents' personal information is confidential and protected. The researcher will create an online and written survey for the respondents to ensure the procedure is straightforward. Data gathering will be conducted through distribution of survey questionnaires to gather information about customers' perceptions regarding the ambience of coffee shops in Tagaytay and its impact on customer satisfaction and revisit intention.

Data Treatment and Analysis

Frequency and percentage approach will be used to identify the demographic background of the respondents. The researcher will begin by weighted mean, transcribing the collected data, reading through the transcripts several times to familiarize with the data, and then identifying and extracting key ideas, concepts, and themes. There the researcher will understand the level of customer satisfaction and revisit intentions by correlation analysis using Pearson's correlation coefficient. These ideas and concepts will be grouped into broader themes, leading to an overall understanding of the phenomenon being studied. Throughout the research process, ethical guidelines such as obtaining informed consent and maintaining confidentiality of participants will be strictly followed.

INTERPRETATION OF RESPONSE AND VARIABLE

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the study conducted. This includes the analysis of the data gathered from the survey as well as their interpretation.

Table 1: Participants` Profile by Age

Age	frequency	%
20 and below	19	12.666667
21 to 25	72	48
26 to 29	49	32.666667
30 and above	10	6.666667
total	150	100

The participants in the study are mostly in the age range of 21-25 years old at 48%. This is followed by those belonging to the age group of 26-29 years old at 32.7%. Those who are aged between 20 and below are at 12.67%. Only 7% constitutes the age bracket 30 and above. This shows that the customers considered in the study are relatively young as they are mostly within the age group of 21 to 25 years old.

Table 2: Participants` Profile by Gender

Gender	frequency	%
Female	75	50
Male	75	50
total	150	100

In terms of gender, both male and female have the same amount of coffee shop consumers. This implies that both men and women enjoy going to coffee shops.

Table 3: Participants' Profile by Occupation

Occupation	frequency	%
Students	89	59.333333
Working	61	40.666667
total	150	100

In terms of occupation, participants are students at 59.33%. Only 40.66% participants have jobs and are working. This means that coffee shops are popular with both students and working people.

Table 4: Participants' Profile by Income Level

Allowance/ Income (Php)	frequency	%
1,000 - Below	23	15.333333
1,001 - 5,000	64	42.666667
5,001 - 10,000	15	10
10,000 - Above	48	32
total	150	100

The table shows that most coffee shop consumers' allowance / income ranges from 1,001 to 5,000 with the percentage of 42.67%. Next are people with 10,000 - above by 32% and the very least are 5,001 to 10,000 with 10%. This means that people who are in the range of 1,001 to 5,000 are the one who goes to coffee shops most of the time.

Table 5: Participants' Profile by Frequency of visiting (weekly)

Frequency of visitation (w)	Frequency	%
Not very Often	50	33.333333
Once a week	45	30
Twice a week	38	25.333333
More than two times a week	17	11.333333
total	150	100

The table shows that 33.33% of the participants visits coffee shop not very often, next are people who visit once a week by 30% then who visit twice a week by 25.33%. Lastly, 11.33% of people who visit more than two times a week. This shows that a lot of the respondents are people who visit coffee shops very often.

Table 6: Participants' Profile by Civil Status

Civil Status	frequency	%
Married	16	10.666667
Single	134	89.333333
total	150	100

With regards to civil status, more than half of the participants are still single at 89.33%. Married participants comprise 10.67% of the total number of participants considered for the study. This manifests that most of the consumers are single.

Verbal Interpretation of the mean

Mean	Interpretation per item	overall mean interpretation
1.00-1.49	strongly disagree	Very low
1.50-2.49	disagree	low
2.50-3.49	neutral	undecided
3.50-4.49	agree	high
4.50-5.00	strongly agree	very high

Table 7: Decorations and artifacts

DECORATIONS & ARTIFACTS	Mean	Verbal interpretation
The concept of the decorations and artifacts improves my first impression on the cafe	4.37	agree
The uniqueness of the decorations and artifacts encourages me to spend more time evaluating the cafe	4.32	agree
The style of the decorations and artifacts encourages me to categorize the cafe as high-class	4.43	agree
The design of the decorations and artifacts affects my satisfaction level towards the cafe	4.41	agree
Overall Level of satisfaction in terms of décor	4.38	High

The table shows that decorations and artifacts have a great impact on the customers satisfaction, same with the results of the study of AbuThahir, S; Krishnapillai, G. (2018) which showed that decoration and artifacts element of the café were noted to have influence towards customer revisit intention to the cafe. Past studies found that customer impression towards a café is based on the design elements that portray uniqueness of the café environment. It was further emphasized that the appropriate choice of decorations and artifacts closely related to the differentiation depicted by the café as a high-class service provider.

Table 8: Lighting

LIGHTING	Mean	Verbal interpretation
The brightness of the lighting allows me to browse through the menu easily	4.38	agree
The dimness of the lighting gave me an intimate / relaxed feeling	4.36	agree
The clarity of the lighting allows me to evaluate the overall ambience of the cafe	4.38	agree
The attractiveness of the lighting (e.g : shape and color of bulb) enhances my perception of the cafe's image.	4.45	agree
Overall level of satisfaction in terms of lighting	4.39	High

The table shows that lighting has a great impact on the customers satisfaction, same with the results of the study of AbuThahir, S; Krishnapillai, G. (2018) which showed that lighting is the most important thing that customers are concerned with in the selection to revisit their preferred cafe. It shows that the lighting elements being the natural pull factor to change customers' perceptions towards their preferred cafe.

Table 9: Music

MUSIC	Mean	Verbal interpretation
The right genre of music influences my mood in a positive manner	4.43	agree
The tempo of the music increases my willingness to wait for my food	4.4	agree
The rhythm of the music enhances my enjoyment	4.44	agree
The appropriate volume of the music helps to reduce my stress level	4.45	agree
Overall level of satisfaction in terms of music	4.43	High

The table shows that music has a great impact on the customers satisfaction, same with the result of the study of AbuThahir, S; Krishnapillai, G. (2018) which showed that music was found to contribute to the customer's revisit intention. This may cause the choice of music selection in the café which leads to endow a modest effect on customer revisit intention.

Table 10: Store layout

STORE LAYOUT	Mean	Verbal interpretation
The accessibility of the store layout enhances my positive evaluation	4.45	agree
The design of the store layout encourages me to walk around and select more food and beverages	4.39	agree
The efficiency of the store layout eases my entry and exit	4.45	agree
The creativeness of the store layout (e.g: seating arrangements) encourages me to stay longer	4.45	agree
Overall level of satisfaction in terms of layout	4.44	High

The table shows that decorations and artifacts have a great impact on the customers satisfaction same with the results of the study of AbuThahir, S; Krishnapillai, G. (2018) which showed that layout & design and it indicated that specially take-away consumers are willing to revisit cafe which are supporting to get in and out within short time,

Table 11: Cleanliness

CLEANLINESS	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The cleanliness of the cafe encourages me to have a positive impression towards the cafe	4.55	Strongly Agree
The cleanliness of the cafe improves my evaluation of the food quality	4.55	Strongly Agree
The cleanliness of the cafe increases my desire to stay longer	4.6	Strongly Agree
The cleanliness of the cafe enhances my overall satisfaction level	4.62	Strongly Agree
Overall level of satisfaction in terms of cleanliness	4.58	Very High

The table shows that cleanliness has a great impact on the customers satisfaction that may affect the customers revisit intention.

Table 12: What is the level of customers' intention to revisit?

REVISIT INTENTIONS	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I would like to consider the cafe as one of my choices in the future	4.27	agree
I would like to invite my friends and family along to the cafe again	4.33	agree
I would like to experience the pleasant feeling in the cafe again	4.45	agree
I would like to build an everlasting relationship with the service provider	4.34	agree
Overall Level of Revisit intention	4.35	high

Table 13: Is there a significant relationship between the level of customer satisfaction and intention to revisit?

Revisit intention vs satisfaction on	Pearson's r	p-value	Verbal Interpretation
decorations	0.726	< .001	Significant
lighting	0.778	< .001	Significant
music	0.697	< .001	Significant
store layout	0.716	< .001	Significant
cleanliness	0.649	< .001	Significant
overall satisfaction	0.796	< .001	Significant

Interpretation

There is a significant and positive relationship between the revisit intentions of the respondents and their level of satisfaction on decorations and artifacts, lighting, music, store layout and cleanliness since the Pearson's correlation coefficients of 0.726, 0.778, 0.697, 0.716 and 0.649 have p-values less than 5% significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. This result indicated that a higher level of satisfaction on decorations and artifacts, lighting, music, store layout and cleanliness would indicate a higher level of revisit intentions and vice versa.

Also, there is a significant and positive relationship between the revisit intentions of the respondents and their overall level of satisfaction since the Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.796 has a p-value less than 5% significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. This result indicated that a higher overall level of satisfaction would indicate a higher level of revisit intentions and vice versa.

Summary

The study was conducted to determine how physical ambience affects the customers satisfaction and their revisit intentions. Specifically, the study sought to describe the demographic characteristics of these customers in terms of age, gender, occupation, income level, frequency of visiting (weekly) and civil status. The study also wanted to know how physical ambience such as decoration and artifacts, lighting, music, store layout, and cleanliness affects the customer satisfaction and their revisit intentions. Moreover, the study wanted to know the different levels of customers' intention to revisit and the significant relationship between the level of customer satisfaction and intention to revisit.

The approach was quantitative because this encompassed a variety of methods, usually numerical and statistical data to explain the relationship of the variables considered in the study and test the validity of the measurements made. The study was conducted in Bag of Beans, Tagaytay Cafe Voi La, Tagaytay Tsokolateria, Tagaytay and through Google Forms. Purposive sampling method (Quota Sampling) was used here, and the participants considered 50 respondents per cafe with a total of 150 respondents. The instrument used in gathering the data was the survey questionnaire online survey and face-to-face survey forms. The survey was conducted personally.

The study found out that most of the cafe consumers were young, ranging between the age of 21-25 years old with an even number of male and female and most were still single. Most of the customers were students and most of them don't visit coffee shops that often.

The study also found out the physical ambience of the coffee shops such as decoration and artifacts, lighting, music, store layout and cleanliness affects the customer satisfaction that can affect the customers revisit intentions. Coffee shops must not only focus on the quality of products but also the quality of physical experience they provide to the customers. There is also a significant relationship between the level of customer satisfaction and intention to revisit.

5. CONCLUSION

This study revealed that cafe ambience had a significant impact on customers satisfaction and revisit intentions. In other words, decorations and artifacts, lighting, music, store layout and cleanliness appear to be major determinants of the revisit intentions of customers.

The customers in Bag of Beans, Tagaytay Cafe Voi La, Tagaytay Tsokolateria, Tagaytay are relatively young. Most of them are students and most are also single. This may be attributed to the fact their main customers are students from nearby schools and looking for a place to stay and for a cup of coffee. Having a good physical ambience in a coffee shop is effective. A coffee shop with good decoration and artifacts, lighting, music, store layout, and cleanliness affects the customer satisfaction and their revisit intentions.

In addition, future researchers are able to select such long-term coffee shops as research settings and examine the impact of coffee shop ambience on revisit intention. Moreover, this study was based on the limited medium scale coffee shops operated in Tagaytay, Philippines and ignored the small- and large-scale coffee shops. Thus, researchers suggest undertaking future research in those settings too.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to extend their appreciation to Ms. Carmela Reyes for the help in the data collected process.

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